

Session 5 - Vectors and epidemiology

Diversity of xylem-feeders and their role in epidemiology of diseases caused by *Xylella fastidiosa*

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Abstract: An increasing number of diseases of fruit crops and ornamental plants have been associated with the xylem-limited bacterium *X. fastidiosa*, which can be transmitted by several species of sharpshooters and spittlebugs. A large diversity of sharpshooters and spittlebugs has been found in association with affected crops, but for most of them the role as vectors of *X. fastidiosa* is unknown. Vector relevance depends not only on ability to transmit the pathogen, but also on ecological and behavioral characteristics in consonance with other epidemiological components of the disease, such as source plants, pathogen dynamics in these hosts, and favorable environmental conditions. For citrus variegated chlorosis, infected citrus trees represent the most important (if not the only) source of inoculum, and four sharpshooter species that commonly feed and reproduce on citrus trees are considered key vectors. For less studied *X. fastidiosa* pathosystems, e.g. plum leaf scald and the newly discovered olive leaf scorch in Brazil and Argentina, there is limited information on vectors and inoculum sources. Weeds, shrubs and trees in the spontaneous vegetation should be investigated as hosts of *X. fastidiosa*. Sharpshooters and spittlebugs inhabiting these plants should be tested as natural carriers of *X. fastidiosa* and for their competence for transmission. Determining what vector species and inoculum sources are relevant for pathogen spread is basic to establish disease management strategies.

Phenology population dynamics and host plants of *Philaenus spumarius* in Italian olive groves

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Abstract: *Philaenus spumarius* is the vector of the CoDiRO strain (subsp. *pauca*) of *X. fastidiosa* in the Apulian olive orchards. Detailed knowledge on ecology and phenology of *P. spumarius* is needed to design control measures aiming at slowing disease progression and assessing the risk in non-infected areas. Open field surveys are conducted in olive orchards in Liguria and Apulia Regions of Italy. Structured population dynamics, host-plant association, seasonal movement between crop and wild species, were investigated by field surveys from March 2016 and are scheduled until the end of 2017. Nymph population in the grass cover was estimated by direct counting in thirty random sampling units (SU) in each olive orchard. Life stage of the insect, host-plant and its phenological stage were recorded. Adults were collected with sweeping net on three different vegetational components: grass cover (30 SU), olive canopy (20 SU), and alternative woody hosts (10 SU). All samplings were conservative to avoid disturbance to spittlebug population. Nymph population peaked in the second half of April in Liguria and at the end of March in Apulia. Early instars were frequently found on plants with basal rosettes, mainly Asteraceae, while later instars moved to upper part of the plant, exploiting many more plant species. Adults show host-shifting during the season as they move from herbaceous hosts to woody plants in the summer and come back to grass cover at the end of the summer.

Bibliography

- Weaver, C. R., and D. R. King. 1954. Meadow spittlebug. Research Bulletin no. 741. Ohio Agricultural Experiment Station, Wooster, OH
- Whittaker, J. B. (1973). Density regulation in a population of *Philaenus spumarius* (L.) (Homoptera: Cercopidae). The Journal of Animal Ecology, 42: 163-172.

Saponari M., Loconsole G., Cornara D., Yokomi R.K., De Stradis A., Boscia D., Bosco D., Martelli G.P., Krugner R., Porcelli F., 2014. Infectivity and Transmission of *Xylella fastidiosa* by *Philaenus spumarius* (Hemiptera: Aphrophoridae) in Apulia, Italy. *J. Econ. Entomol.* 107(4): 1316-1319.

EFSA (European Food Safety Authority), 2016. Workshop on *Xylella fastidiosa*: knowledge gaps and research priorities for the EU. EFSA supporting publication 2016:EN-1039. 74 pp.

Seasonal pattern hosts and abundance of the potential vectors of *Xylella fastidiosa* in Mallorca

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Abstract: The plant pathogen *X. fastidiosa* (Proteobacteria: Xanthomonadaceae) was detected in the Balearic Islands (Mallorca, Menorca and Ibiza) in October 2016. Since then, a surveillance of the potential vector species that are included in the suborder Cicadomorpha has been conducted. The sampling was carried out in different crops from March 2017, including olive, almond, citrus and vineyards of Mallorca, as well as on the herbaceous vegetation of each sample site. Immatures and adults were sampled biweekly in each plot by using general techniques, such as direct observation, sweeping net and vacuum. Collected adults were identified to species level and mouth parts and cibarium were preserved for molecular detection of *X. fastidiosa* by PCR (analysis still ongoing). Preliminary results showed that several species of the family Aphrophoridae were the most frequent and abundant in the selected orchards, particularly *Neophilaenus campestris* and *Phylaenus spumarius*. Nymphs of these species were found from early to late April only and showed preference for particular herbaceous plant species. Adults were also collected from early April and the sampling is still ongoing. We present data on the presence of potential adults vectors in herbaceous plants and crop trees for each month from March to October 2016 and discuss about the impact on *X. fastidiosa* transmission in the Balearic islands.

Bibliography

Almeida RPP and Purcell AH, 2006. Patterns of *Xylella fastidiosa* colonization on the precibarium of sharpshooter vectors relative to transmission to plants. *Annals of the Entomological Society of America*, 99, 884–890.

Cornara, Daniele *et al.* "Spittlebugs as Vectors of *Xylella fastidiosa* in Olive Orchards in Italy." *Journal of Pest Science* 90.2 (2017): 521–530.

EFSA PLH Panel (EFSA Panel on Plant Health), 2015a. Scientific Opinion on the risks to plant health posed by *Xylella fastidiosa* in the EU territory, with the identification and evaluation of risk reduction options. *EFSA Journal* 2015;13(1):3989, 262 pp. doi:10.2903/j.efsa.2015.3989. Available online: <http://www.efsa.europa.eu/en/efsajournal/pub/3989>

Elbeaino T, *et al.* 2014. Identification of three potential insect vectors of *Xylella fastidiosa* in Southern Italy. *Phytopathologia Mediterranea*, 53(1), 126–130.

Lopes, J. *et al.* 2014. A survey of potential insect vectors of the plant pathogenic bacterium *Xylella fastidiosa* in three regions of Spain. *Spanish Journal of Agricultural Research*, [S.I.], 12, (3), 795-800

Redak, R. A. *et al.* 2003. The biology of xylem fluid-feeding insect vectors of *Xylella fastidiosa* and their relation to disease epidemiology. *Annu. Rev. Entomol.* 2004. 49:243–70

Saponari M., *et al.*, 2014. Infectivity and Transmission of *Xylella fastidiosa* by *Philaenus spumarius* (Hemiptera: Aphrophoridae) in Apulia. *Journal of Economic Entomology* 107(4).